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17	Hope and Humor as Predictors of Health among Elderly Bhanu Pratap Yadav & Madhurima Pradhan Lucknow, U.P.	88-93
18	Pardoning Power of the President in India: A Judicial Approach Devesh Saraswat, Aligarh, U.P.	94-100
19	Usage Pattern of Tirunelveli District Central Library Users: A Study E. Sugirtha Kumar, Tirunelveli	101-108
20	Library Automation in School Libraries in Kolkata: A Need-Based Analysis of The Present Scenario Tapas Pal, Ranchi, Jharkhand	109-114
21	ICT Infrastructures and Human Resource Pattern in Central Libraries of Jadavpur University and University of Calcutta: A Comparative Study Joydeb Das, Purba Medinipur, West Bengal & Durga Sankar Rath, Midnapore, West Bengal	115-129
22	Scientometric Study of Solar Power Generation in India with Special References to Citation Analysis S.Elumalai, S. Jeyachitra, Tiruchirappalli, Tamil Nadu & J. Santhi, Tirupathur, Tamil Nadu	130-134
23	Scientometric Analysis of Greenhouse Effect Research Output: A Study Mohanathan P & N. Rajendran, Tamil Nadu	135-141
24	Dinesh Chandra Sen's Two Books: 'Behula' and 'Phullora' Pallab Kumar Sadhu, Santiniketan, West Bengal	142-147
25	A Study of Relationship between Teacher Effectiveness and Psychological Capital among Secondary School Teachers Shubhpreet Kaur & Pushpinder Kaur, Patiala, Punjab	148-150
26	Crisis and Media Narrative: An Analysis of Media Reportage of 2010 Kashmir Unrest Irfan Hashim & Sabeha Mufti, Srinagar	151-158
27	Analysis of Carbon and Nutrient Storage of Soil in Various Land Use Systems in Madhya Pradesh Tarun Kumar Thakur, D. Namdeo & Anita Thakur, Amarkantak, M.P.	159-163
28	Health and Nutritional Status of Gond Children Mehul Chauhan Mandla, Madhya Pradesh	164-170
29	Issues and Challenges of MGNREGA to Reaching Rural Poor- A Sociological Study (With special reference to Tumkur District) Siddagangaiah.S.G, Tiptur & Nagaraja.S., Tumakuru, Karnataka	171-178
30	Societal Health Concern: Exploring Perceptions on Physical Activity among College Students Nagaraja. S., Tumakuru, Karnataka & Siddagangaiah.S.G. Tumakuru, Tiptur	179-183
31	An Empirical Study of The Deviance In College Girl-Students in Urban Space (With Special Reference to The Students of Maharani Laxmi Bai Government College of Excellence, Gwalior) Laxmi Gupta, Dholpur, Rajasthan	184-193
32	Diabetes Mellitus in Mahadev Range of Kashmir Himalayas: A Geographical Analysis G.M. Rather, Kashmir	194-201
33	Educational Status of Bundi District: A Geographical Study Sandeep Yadav & Zuber Khan Bundi, Rajasthan	202-210
34	Rural Livelihood Diversification and Household Well-Being: A Study of Kulageri, Bagalkot Vimit Sankhala, Bagalkot, Karnataka & Savitri Patidar, Udaipur, Rajasthan	211-217
35	Technological Needs of Rural Women in Processing and Preservation of Fruits and Vegetables at Chomu, Jaipur Mamta Jat, Kesar Chayal & Lalita Vatia, Jaipur, Rajasthan	218-222

Dinesh Chandra Sen's Two Books: 'Behula' and 'Phullora'

Abstract

Mangalkavya of the middle ages has been a topic of discussion and debate among the researchers of the world. As a result there has also been a steady rise in readership of Mangalkavya as more and more people have started reading it. Previous studies have revealed that Mangalkavya was composed from 15th to 18th century A.D. and it is regarded as a part of history of the middle ages. Dinesh chandraSen (1866-1939) is one such historian, who keeping in mind the narrative tradition of Manasamangal and Chandimangal composed the prose narratives of Behula(1907) and Phullora(1907) in the first decade of the 20th century. It was only possible for a true patriot like Dinesh chndraSen to represent these two female characters in stories that not only reflected the tradition and culture of Bengal but also reflected the nationalistic fervour of India. This study seeks to reveal whether in his endeavour Dinesh chandraSen had shown any originality and novelty keeping in mind the European/ Western trend of comprehending literature and history.

Keywords: Bengali History, Representation of Past, Self Pride, National Literature, Historicity, Narrative of Mangalkavya, Behula, Phullora, Prose Narrative, Recovering History, Indigenous Culture, Analysis of Manuscripts, Glorious Period, Dinesh Chandrasen.

Introduction

After the creation of MangalKavya, related criticism did not stop. This discourse saw the gradual rise of a particular type of perspective. In this regard David L Curley's book "Poetry and History: Bengali MangalKavya and Social Change in Pre-colonial Bengal"(2008) is worth mentioning. Another mentionable book is JawharSircar's "The Construction of the Hindu Identity in Medieval Western Bengal: The Role of Popular cults". The 12th chapter of this book entitled 'The Role of MangalKavya' is especially important. France Bhattacharya's "The NathSampraday and the Manasa Story" and Tony K. Stuart's "The Process of Surface Narrative: The ManasaBhasan" are important research works in this regard. Apart from theseMangalKavya related discourses could be seen in many books and articles and magazines (Tobu Eklavya/ MangalKavyaBisheshsankha/ edited: DipankarMallick and MangalKavya and Mangalcharcha/ edited Tapas Bhowmik). These writings mainly analysed Mangalakavya from various perspectives like folk-history, contemporary social life, the economy of the period as shown in the MangalaaKavya etc. These discourses show us the approximate dates of composition of these are from 15th century to 18th century. These studies have shown the different aspects of MangalKavya as well as the varied scope it encompasses. MangalKavya is pretty well received in the modern period as well. We have seen that modern Bengali literature has been tremendously influenced by the literature of middle ages. However our research area does not concern the whole of the medieval period but rather focuses on the study of Mangalakavya. We have seen that in the first 50 years of the 20th century many literary works have come into shape in the model of the narrative of Mangalakavya. Most of these works have focussed on particular incidents, characters and sometimes on the journey as well. This study intends to deal with these issues and we start this discussion with Dinesh Chandra Sen.

Review of Literature

Dinesh chandraSen's literary practice related discussion is mainly dependent on his popular book "Bangabhasa o sahitya" with the background of the narrative framework of Mangalkavya, the significance of Dinesh chandraSen's work has been analysed and evaluated by some

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